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ASSESSMENT OF *IN VITRO* ANTIOXIDANT AND ANTIHAEMOLYTIC ACTIVITIES IN *TRITICUM AESTIVUM* GRASS AND *CARICA PAPAYA* LEAVES

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ABSTRACT

The study deals with the comparative evaluation of various extracts of *Triticum aestivum* (Wheat) grass and *Carica papaya* (Papaya) leaves by phytochemical screening followed by antioxidant and antihaemolytic activities as revealed by various parameters such as reducing power, nitric oxide (NO) scavenging activity, diphenyl picrylhydrazine (DPPH) free radical scavenging activity, superoxide dismutase assay, H₂O₂ and hypotonic solution induced haemolysis assay. The phytochemical screening showed high flavonoids, phenolic and alkaloids content which indicates antioxidant strength of the extract. In wheatgrass and papaya leaves n-butanol and aqueous extracts have high scavenging activities compared to ethyl acetate and petroleum ether extracts. All the four extracts (petroleum ether, ethyl acetate, n-butanol, aqueous) scavenge free radicals to a certain extent but n-butanol and aqueous extract exhibited more potential effect among all four extracts. Thus it can be concluded that there two potential extracts could be explored for further *in vivo* studies.

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INTRODUCTION

Many abnormalities of RBCs make the cells fragile resulting in reducing number of cells leading to haemolytic anaemia. It may be caused due to various causative agents such as chemical agents e.g. lead or arsenic, ionizing radiation, malaria¹. Malaria-associated acute haemolysis, is one of the major life-threatening cause of death in *P. falciparum* and *P. vivax*, occurs between 1 and 4% of hospitalized patients with a mortality that can be up to 45%^{2,3}. The pathogenesis of malaria-associated acute haemolysis has suggested involvement of cyto adherence of infected RBC and inflammatory response as well as oxidative stress through generation of reactive oxygen intermediates by host cells⁴.

A medicinal plant as defined by the World Health Organization (WHO) is a plant whose one or more parts of it contain substances that can be used for therapeutic purposes and their precursors are used for the synthesis of drugs as it contains enormous number of secondary metabolites⁵.

T. aestivum (wheat) belongs to Poaceae family. It is the most edible cereal. Nowadays, researchers have known wheatgrass is nutrient-rich grass. It is many times rich in vitamins, minerals and proteins as compared to seed kernel or mature cereal plant⁶. Papaya (*Carica papaya*) is the fruit belongs to the genus *Carica*⁷. It was first cultivated in Mexico and native to tropics of America⁸.

Oxidative damage of cells and bio molecules due to oxygen/nitrogen species (ROS/RNS) is reduced by antioxidants⁹. An antioxidant can scavenge the free radical's due to their redox hydrogen donors and singlet oxygen quencher¹⁰. The free radicals can be scavenged by the plants and synthetic (BHT, BHA, etc) antioxidants¹¹. Antioxidants can be classified into two major groups i.e., enzymatic and non-enzymatic. The enzymatic antioxidants which are produced endogenously include nitric oxide reductase, superoxide dismutase, catalase, glutathione peroxidase. The non-enzymatic antioxidants include tocopherols, carotenoids, ascorbic acid, flavonoids and tannins which are obtained naturally from plant¹².

Reactive oxygen species (ROS) and reactive nitrogen species (RNS) play an important role in many biological processes and are involved in host defense. Overproduction of these species such as hydroxyl radical (OH), hydrogen peroxide (H₂O₂), superoxide anions (O₂⁻), and nitric oxide (NO), as well as peroxy nitrite contributes to the immunopathology of a vast variety of condition including inflammatory diseases, cancer, atherosclerosis, diabetes mellitus, hypertension, AIDS, and aging¹³. A wide range of antioxidants from both natural and synthetic origin has been proposed for use in the treatment of various human diseases. In recent decades, many researchers are interested in medicinal plants for evaluation of antioxidant phytochemicals such as phenolics, flavonoids and tannins, as they have the potential role in the prevention of human disease¹⁴. Thus the present study aims in evaluating the potential potent which has good antioxidant and antihaemolytic activity so that it could be used to combat haemolytic anaemia.

MATERIALS AND METHODS:

Qualitative phytochemical screening of aqueous extract of *T. aestivum* grass and *C. papaya* leaves:

The grass of *T. aestivum* was cultivated collected and leaves of *C. papaya* were collected from ITM University, Turari Campus, chopped, dried in shade and powdered with a mechanical grinder. The powdered leaf was weighed 10g and was dissolved in 50 ml distilled water. The flask was put in an orbital shaker for 48 hrs. It was filtered through Whatman no. 1 filter paper. The residue was thrown away while the filtrate was exposed to air and allowed to evaporate to obtain the concentrated extract.

Preliminary phytochemical screening of the extracts was performed for the presence of alkaloids, flavonoids, steroids, tannins, saponin, phenol and using the standard procedures.

Alkaloids:

To 1 ml of extract, 2-3 drops of Wagner's reagent were added. The appearance of pale or white precipitate indicated the presence of alkaloids¹⁵.

Steroids:

To 2 ml of extract, 2 ml of chloroform and 2 ml of concentration sulphuric acid was added. Tubes were shaken and allowed to stand. Formation of red colour chloroform layer indicates the presence of steroids¹⁶.

Tannins:

3 ml of extracts was treated with 1% lead acetate solution. A red or yellow colour precipitate was formed, indicating the presence of tannins¹⁵.

Saponins:

To 3 ml of extracts, few drops of sodium bicarbonate was added and shaken vigorously for 3 min. Honey comb froth was formed, showing the presence of saponins¹⁵.

Phenolic:

To 1 ml of extracts, 2 ml of distilled water and few drops of 10% ferric chloride solution were added. Formation of blue or green colour indicates the presence of phenols¹⁵.

Flavonoids:

To 2 ml of each extract was added few drops of 20% sodium hydroxide, formation of intense yellow colour is observed, by adding 70% hydrochloric acid yellow colour was disappeared. Disappearance of yellow colour indicates the presence of flavonoids in the extract¹⁷.

Extraction of Plant material

50g of powder was weighed and extracted with soxhlet apparatus using various solvent according to their polarity i.e. petroleum ether, ethyl acetate, n-butanol and water. After solvent extraction, it was evaporated to obtain a powdered extract for various biochemical analyses.

Reducing Power assay

2.5 ml phosphate buffer (0.2M, pH 6.6) and 2.5 ml 1% potassium ferrocyanide was mixed in 1 ml of different fraction of plant extract at various concentration (20, 80, 120, 240 µg/ml) diluted in distilled water. The test tubes were incubated at 50°C in water bath for 10 min. followed by addition of 2.5 ml 10% TCA (Tricarboxylic acid) and centrifuge at 3000 rpm for 10 min. 2.5 ml of upper layer was collected, and 2.5 ml distilled water was added followed by 0.5 ml 0.1% FeCl₃ (freshly prepared). Increase in absorbance was measured at 700 nm against a suitable blank¹⁸.

NO radical Scavenging activity

NO radical scavenging activities of plant extract in different fraction were examined by Royer *et al.*, (2011)¹⁹. To 200 µl sodium nitroprusside (5Mm), 800 µl extracts (0.1-1 mg/ml) was added dissolved in PBS (25 mM, pH 7.4). The mixture was incubated for 2.5 hr at 37°C under normal light and followed dark incubation for 20 min., 600 µl Griess reagent (1% sulphanilamide, 0.1 % naphthyl ethylene diamine hydrochloride in 2% phosphoric acid) was added and incubated for 40 min. at room temperature and absorbance was measured at 540 nm against a suitable blank (2ml H₂O and 0.6 ml Griess reagent). Control (1.6 ml H₂O, 400µl SNP and 600µl Griess reagent was prepared and percent of inhibition was calculated by using this equation.

$$\text{Percentage inhibition} = \text{OD of control} - (\text{OD of extract} / \text{OD of control}) \times 100 \text{ ----- (1)}$$

DPPH free radical scavenging activity

DPPH free radical scavenging activity of plant extracts in different fraction was examined by Blois method²⁰ with minor modification. To 2ml of plant extract taken at various Concentration (20-100µg/ml), 1 ml of DPPH solution (0.1Mm in methanol) was added, shaken well and incubated at 37° C for 30 min in dark. Decrease in absorbance was measured at 517 nm spectrophotometrically against a suitable blank and control tube contains methanol and DPPH. The percentage of inhibition was calculated by using equation 1.

Superoxide Dismutase (SOD) Assay

This assay was done by the method of Kakkar *et al.*, (1984)²¹. Fresh wheatgrass (0.5g), were ground with 5.0 ml of sodium phosphate buffer (50mM, pH 6.4) centrifuge at 2000g for 10 min. and supernatant were collected used for the assay. Assay mixture contained 1.2 ml of Sodium pyrophosphate buffer (0.025M, pH 8.3), 0.1 ml of phenazine methosulphate (186µM), 0.3 ml of nitroblue tetrazolium (300µM), 0.2 ml of plant extract at different concentration (20-100µg/ml) and distilled water in a total volume of 2.8ml. The reaction was initiated by addition of 0.2ml NADH (780 µM). The mixture was incubated at 30°C for 90 secs, 1 ml glacial acetic acid to stop the reaction. Reaction mixture was shaken with 4 ml n-butanol, and allowed to stand for 10 min. It was centrifuged at 2000g for 10 min. and butanol layer was collected. The intensity of chromogen n-butanol layer was measured at 560 nm. The percent of inhibition was calculated by using this equation.

$$\text{Percentage inhibition} = (\text{OD of control} - \text{OD of extract} / \text{OD of control} \times \text{mg of protein}) \times 100$$

Antihaemolytic activity/ Membrane stabilizing activity

The following two methods were used for conducting this *invitro* membrane stabilizing assay:

Hypotonic solution-induced haemolysis:

This method was done by method of Shinde *et al.*, (1999)²². 5 ml of whole blood of a healthy person in heparinized tube was collected. The blood was centrifuged at 3000g for 10 min. supernatant was removed and RBCs were washed three times with sodium chloride isotonic solution (154 mM NaCl) in 10 mM Sodium phosphate buffer (pH 7.4) through centrifugation using the same volume as supernatant. Finally, RBCs were resuspended in the same volume of isotonic buffer solution. After that, 0.5 ml of RBCs suspension was mixed with 5 ml of hypotonic solution (50mM NaCl in 10mM sodium phosphate buffer pH 7.4) containing 0.5 ml plant extracts (10mg/ml). The control sample was prepared by 0.5 ml suspension mixed with hypotonic buffered saline. The mixture was incubated for 10 min. at room temperature, centrifuged at 3000g for 10 min. and the optical density of supernatant was measured at 540nm.

H₂O₂ induced haemolysis:

This method was done by Ebrahimzadeh *et al.*, (2009)²³. 5ml whole blood was collected in heparinized tube, centrifuged (10 min. at 1500g) RBCs separate out from plasma and buffy coat three washes in 10 volumes of 10 mM/L PBS. Washed RBCs diluted in PBS to obtained 4 % suspension. To 2ml RBCs suspension, 1ml Plant extracts (10mg/ml) incubated for 5 min. at room temperature, 0.5ml H₂O₂ was added shaken well and incubate at 37°C for 30 min. centrifuged supernatant was collected and take absorbance at 540 nm. Percentage inhibition of was calculated by using equation 1.

Statistical analysis:

All data were expressed as mean \pm standard deviation from three replicate (n=3) experiments. The free radical scavenging activity was calculated by using Graph Pad Prism 7 ink. Software

RESULTS

Preliminary phytochemical screening

The qualitative test for alkaloids, flavonoids, tannins, phenols, saponins, and steroids from aqueous extract of *T. aestivum* grass and *C. papaya* leaves were investigated. Table 1 represents the phytochemical screening of *T.aestivum* grass and *C. papaya* leaves. Results revealed the presence of alkaloids, flavonoids, tannins, phenols, saponins, steroids. The phytochemical analysis of *T. aestivum* and *C. papaya* revealed the presence of alkaloids, flavonoids, tannins, phenols, saponins, steroids compounds.

Table 1: Phytochemical screening of *T.aestivum* grass and *C. papaya* leaves in aqueous extract.

Species	Alkaloids	Flavonoids	Tannins	Phenols	Saponins	Steroids
<i>T.aestivum</i>	++	+++	++	+	+	+
<i>C. papaya</i>	+	+	+	+	+	+

+: low, ++: Moderate, +++: high.

Reducing Power assay

Fig. 1 shows the reducing power of four extracts of wheatgrass and papaya leaves at 700 nm. Highest reducing abilities were observed in aqueous extract of wheatgrass (1.01) and papaya leaves (1.36) respectively followed by n-butanol extracts of wheatgrass (0.76) and papaya leaves (0.97) respectively at 240 μ g/ml concentration.

NO radical Scavenging activity

Fig. 2 shows the NO scavenging activity of wheatgrass and papaya leaves in four extracts. The maximum scavenging activity in papaya leaves n-butanol extracts 74.28 and wheatgrass aqueous extract 60.7 at 1 mg/ml. as compared to others extracts.

DPPH radical scavenging activity:

Fig 3 shows the DPPH radical scavenging activity. The highest scavenging activity was obtained in wheatgrass n-butanol extract (60.3 at 100 μ g/ml) followed by ethyl acetate extract (52.7 at 80 μ g/ml). In papaya leaves aqueous extract maximum inhibition was 34.9 followed by n- butanol extract 31.7 at 100 μ g/ml.

WGPE-Wheatgrass petroleum ether	PLPE- Papaya leaves petroleum ether
WGEA-Wheatgrass ethyl acetate	PLEA- Papaya leaves ethyl acetate
WGNB-Wheatgrass n- butanol	PLNB- Papaya leaves n-butanol,
WGA-Wheatgrass aqueous	PLA-Papaya leaves aqueous

Fig. 1 Reducing power of wheatgrass and papaya leaves in four extracts.

WGPE-Wheatgrass petroleum ether PLPE- Papaya leaves petroleum ether
 WGEA-Wheatgrass ethyl acetate PLEA- Papaya leaves ethyl acetate
 WGNB-Wheatgrass n- butanol PLNB- Papaya leaves n-butanol,
 WGA-Wheatgrass aqueous PLA-Papaya leaves aqueous

Fig.2 Nitric oxide scavenging activity of wheatgrass and papaya leaves in four extracts.

WGPE-Wheatgrass petroleum ether PLPE- Papaya leaves petroleum ether
 WGEA-Wheatgrass ethyl acetate PLEA- Papaya leaves ethyl acetate
 WGNB-Wheatgrass n- butanol PLNB- Papaya leaves n-butanol,
 WGA-Wheatgrass aqueous PLA-Papaya leaves aqueous

Fig. 3 DPPH radical scavenging activity of wheatgrass and papaya leaves in four extracts.

Superoxide dismutase (SOD) assay:

Superoxide dismutase activities from the fresh samples were examined at various concentration of extract. Table 2 represents the SOD activity. Percentage of inhibition was found to be maximum at 60- 80 µg/ml.

Table.2: Superoxide dismutase activity of *T. aestivum*.

S.No.	Concentration (µg/ml)	% Inhibition
1	20	21.9±0.6
2	40	37.1±3.7
3	60	40.9±0.63
4	80	39.3±2.2
5	100	36.5±2.5

Values are expressed as mean± SD (n=3).

Antihaemolytic activities

Table 3: Antihaemolytic activity results of *Triticum aestivum* grass.

Fractions	H ₂ O ₂ induced antihaemolysis activity (10mg/ml)	Hypotonic solution induced antihaemolysis (10mg/ml)
Control	100%	100%
petroleum ether	65%	62%
ethyl acetate	68%	68%
n-butanol	82%	75%

Antihaemolytic and membrane stabilizing activities are depicted in table 3. In case of hypotonic solution induced haemolysis, the maximum level of membrane stabilizing activity was observed by n-butanol fraction of wheatgrass which was 75% by H₂O₂ induced haemolysis and 82% by hypotonic solution induced haemolysis. The minimum antihaemolytic activity was exhibited by petroleum ether extract of wheatgrass. The ranges of antihaemolytic activities of all extracts were between 65-82%.

DISCUSSION

Plants produce secondary metabolites which possess the capability to perform antioxidant, anticancer and antihaemolytic activities. Alkaloids, phenolics and terpenoids are three major compounds from plants²⁴.

Plants derived antioxidants are better than synthetic antioxidants and they do not produce any side effects. Non-polar compounds have a better capability to extract polyphenols as compared to polar compounds. There is no single assay specific enough to determine the antioxidant potential of a sample, thus multiple assays need to be performed²⁵.

Antioxidant activity may result by the synergy between various mechanism occurring in the living system owing to the complex nature of phytochemicals present²⁶.

Reducing power is a significant indicator of the potential antioxidant activity²⁷. The presence of reductones which exert the antioxidant activity by breaking the free radical chain by donating hydrogen atom in the sample might cause reduction in Fe²⁺/Fe³⁺, spectrophotometer at 700nm²⁸. Reducing power increased with increase in extract concentration. Thus, this plant may have a higher amount of reductones and hence the antioxidant property.

In vitro inhibition of nitric oxide is a measure of antioxidant activity of plant drugs. Nitric oxide is an important chemical mediator generated by endothelial cells, macrophages, neurons etc. wheatgrass found to be an efficient scavenger of nitric oxide radical in sodium nitro prusside. It represents that this plant has a significant property of scavenging nitric oxide. It may be water soluble compound like phenolics with potent free reduced scavenging effect²⁹.

Nitric Oxide (NO) released from SNP (sodium nitroprusside) has a strong NO character which can alter the structure and function of many cellular components. The wheatgrass extract of 0.5 mg/ml gave a better NO scavenging activity as compared to papaya leaves. Leading to reduction of nitrite concentration in the assay. The concentration dependent pattern showed as the most effective concentration for NO scavenging activity. The toxicity of NO increases when it reacts with superoxide to form peroxynitrite ion. The present study shows that wheatgrass extract of 0.5 mg/ml has a potential nitric oxide scavenging activity.

DPPH free radical has been widely used to test the antioxidant power of various natural products³⁰. It is a marker of free radicals originating in lipids³¹. In the present study, various extracts of *T. aestivum* and *C. papaya* at varied concentration were tested in reducing the stable DPPH (fig.3). *T. aestivum* extract had high scavenging activity as compared to *C. papaya* extracts. IC₅₀ was calculated which is the amount of sample needed to scavenge 50% of the initial concentration of free radical. Lower the IC₅₀ higher is the scavenging activity. Results of IC₅₀ values revealed that wheatgrass extract of increased polarity was more powerful and depleted the initial concentration of DPPH by 50%³². DPPH is a stable free radical that can accept an electron of hydrogen radical to become a stable diamagnetic molecule³³. In the present study, the extract had significant effect with the increase in concentration of sample from 20 to 100 µg/ml. Ethyl acetate fractions showed better results which may be due to the presence of high flavonoid content as extraction^{34,35}.

SOD is thought to play a very important role in protecting living cells against toxic damage to free radicals. The enzyme catalyses the dismutation of two superoxide radicals (O₂⁻) into O₂ and H₂O₂³⁶. Table 2 shows the activity of pure superoxide dismutase assay at different concentration. Result indicates maximum inhibition at 60-80µg/ml concentration. This concentration is effective to reduce O₂⁻ radical. Since super oxide dismutase is generally assayed in partially purified preparation, the addition of acetic acid to stop reaction helps to dissolve the protein²¹.

Antihaemolytic activity of quercetin and the relation between non-chelating activity against oxidative damage to erythrocyte membrane by flavonoid has been reported³⁷. The increased antihaemolytic activity of test sample implies that leaf extract contain flavonoid & glycosides can guard RBC from free radical mediated haemolysis³⁸. Binding of flavonoids to the RBCs membrane inhibit lipid peroxidation and simultaneously enhances their integrity against lysis³⁹. Antihaemolytic and membrane stabilizing activity are depicted in table 2. In case of hypotonic solution induced haemolysis, the maximum level of membrane stabilizing activity was by n-butanol fraction of wheatgrass (75%) and by H₂O₂ induced haemolysis (82%). The minimum antihaemolytic activity was exhibited by petroleum ether extract of wheatgrass.

Thus, membrane stabilizing experiment can serve as an indicator to screen out the anti-inflammatory agent which can prevent the release of phosphatase that inhibits the formation of inflammatory mediators²². Antihaemolytic activity may be attributed to high flavonoid and phenolic content^{40,41} which shows considerable anti-inflammatory activity^{42,43,44}.

CONCLUSION

The present work supports the earlier reports of phytochemical analysis of plant extracts of *Triticum aestivum* grass and *Carica papaya* leaves. The study was projected in *in vitro* screening of a potent antioxidant and antihemolytic agent. The antihemolytic and antioxidant activity is an indicator of antianemic potential of the extract.

Recommended future Research:

Further investigation both *in vivo* and *in vitro* needs to be explored for antianemic and antioxidant efficacy of the plant extracts.

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Conflict of interest.

The authors have no conflicts of interest.

REFERENCES

- Ross and Wilson. 2006. Anatomy and physiology in health and illness. 7th ed. Elsevier: Churchill Livingstone: 70-71.
- Spottiswoode N, Duffy PE, Drakesmith H. Iron, anemia and hepcidin in malaria. *Front Pharmacol*, 2014;5.
- Rolling T, Agbenyega T, S. Issifou. Delayed haemolysis after treatment with parenteral artesunate in African children with severe malaria—a double-center prospective study. *J Infect Dis* 2014;209(12):1921–1928.
- Lang F, Abed M, Lang E, Foller M. Oxidative stress and suicidal erythrocyte death. *Antioxid Redox Signal*, 2014;2:138-153.
- Ogamba JO, Eze NA, Ogamba SE, Chilaka KC. *Trop J Med Res*, 2010;142:1-6.
- Tirgarl PR, Thumber BL, Desai TR. Isolation characterization and Biologocical evaluation of iron chelator from *Triticum aestivum* (Wheatgrass). *Int J Pharm biosci*, 2011; 2:288-296.
- Eno AE, Owo OI, Itam EH, Konya RS. Blood pressure Depression by the fruit juice of *Carica papaya* [L] in renal and DOCA-induced Hypertension in the Rat. *J Phytother Res*, 2000;9(4):235-239.
- Everette BM. Carpaïne on Alkaloid of carica papaya. *J Chem Pharmacol*, 2003;22(5): 281-298.
- Fiorentino A, D'Abrosca B, Pacifico S, Mastellone C, Piscopo V, Caputo R, Monaco P, 2008. Isolation and structure elucidation of antioxidant polyphenols from quince (*Cydonia vulgaris*) peels. *J Agric Food Chem*, 2008;56:2660-2667.
- Wu YY, Li W, Xu Y, Jin EH, Tu YY. Evaluation of the antioxidant effects of four main thea flavin derivative through hemiluminescence and DNA damage analyses. *J Zhejiang Univ Sci B* 2011;12(9):744-751.
- Mbaebe BO, Edeoga HO, Afolayan AJ. Phytochemical analysis and antioxidants activities of aqueous stem bark extract of *Schotialatifolia* Jacq. *Asian Pac J Trop Biomed*, 2012;2(2):118-124.
- Naskar S, Islam A, Mazumdar UK, Saha P, Haldar PK, Gupta M. In vitro and In vivo antioxidant potential of hydromethanolic extract of *Phoenix dactylifera* fruits. *J Sci Res*, 2010;2(1):144-157.
- Darley-Usmar V, Wiseman H, Halliwell B. Nitric oxide and oxygen radicals: a question of balance. *FEBS let*, 1995;369(2-3):131-135.
- Lee S, Suh S, Kin S. Protective effects of green tea polyphenol (-) – epigallocatechingallate against hippocampal neuronal damage alter transient global ischemia in gerbils. *Neuro sci Lett*, 2000;287:191-194.
- Harborne JB. 1973. Phytochemical methods. 2nd ed. London: Chapman and Hall Ltd 149-88.
- Kumar S, Sharma UK, Sharma AK, Pandey AK. Protective efficacy of salanum xanthocarpum root extract against free radical damage. *Phytochemical analysis and antioxidant effect. Cell Mol Bio*, 2012;58(1):174-181.
- Prabhavathi RM, Prasad MP, Jayaramu M. Studies on qualitative and quantitative phytochemical analysis of *cissusquadragularis*. *Adv appl sci res*, 2016; 7(4):11-17.
- Benzie IF, Strain JJ. The ferric reducing ability of plasma (FRAP) as a measure of “antioxidant power”: the FRAP assay. *Anal biochem*, 1996;239(1):70-76.
- Royer M, Diouf PN, Stevanovic T. **Polyphenol contents and radical scavenging capacities of red maple (*Acer rubrum* L.) extracts.** *Food Chem. Toxicol*, 2011;49(9): 2180-2188.
- Esmaili MA, Sonboli A. Antioxidant, free radical scavenging activities of *Salvia brachyantha* and its protective effect against oxidative cardiac cell injury. *Foodchemtoxico*, 2010;48(3):846-853.
- Kakkar P, Das B, Viswanathan PN. A modified spectrophotometric assay of superoxide dismutase. *Ind J Biochem Biophys*, 1984;21(2):130-132.
- Shinde UA, Phadke AS, Nair AM, Mungantiwar AA, Dikshit VJ, Saraf MN. Membrane stabilizing activity — a possible mechanism of action for the anti-inflammatory activity of *Cedrus deodarata* wood oil. *Fitoterapia*, 1999;70:251-257.
- Ebrahimzadeh MA, Nabavi SF, Eslami B, Nabavi SM. Antioxidant and antihemolytic potentials of *Physospermum cornubiense* (L.) DC. *Pharmacologyonline*, 2009;3:394-403.
- Harborne JB. Classes and functions of secondary products from plants. *Chemicals from plants*, 1999;1-25.
- Kim E, Oh, CS, Koh SH, Kim HS, Kang KS, Park PS, Jang MJ, Lee HR, Park IK. Antifungal Activities after vaporization of Ajowan (*Trachyspermum ammi*) and Allspice (*Pimenta dioica*) Essential Oils and Blends of Their Constituents against three Aspergillus Species. *J Essent Oil Re*, 2016;28:252-259.

26. Hall CA, Cuppet SL. 1997. Structure activities of natural antioxidants. In: Antioxidant Methodology in vivo and in vitro Concepts. Aruoma OI, Cuppet SL (eds). Champaign IL 2-29.
27. Oliveira, I, Sousa A, Ferreira IC, Bento A, Estevinho L, Pereira JA. Total phenols, antioxidant potential and antimicrobial activity of walnut (*Juglans regia* L.) green husks. Food chemtoxico, 2008;46(7):2326-2331.
28. Nair VD, Panneerselvam R, Gopi R. Studies on methanolic extract of *Rauvolfia* species from Southern Western Ghats of India—In vitro antioxidant properties, characterisation of nutrients and phytochemicals. Ind Crops Prod, 2012;39:17-25.
29. Pacher P, Beckman JS, Liaudet L. Nitric oxide and peroxynitrite: in health and disease. Physiol Rev, 2007;87:315–424.
30. Brand-Williams W, Cuvelier ME, Berset CL. Use of a free radical method to evaluate antioxidant activity. LWT-Food sciTechnol, 1995;28(1):25-30.
31. Yasuda T, Inaba A, Ohmori M, Endo T, Kubo S, Ohsawa K. Urinary metabolites of gallic acid in rats and their radical scavenging effect on DPPH. J Nat Prod, 2000;63: 1444-1446.
32. Krishna TM, Shiva D, Keerthi D, Nandini A, Aswaq A, Reddy T. *In vitro* evaluation of antioxidant properties of *Cucumis melo* L. extracts of leaves and fruit. Int J Pharma Bio Sci, 2013;4(1):705-712.
33. Bijaya IM, Bikash B. Antioxidant capacity and phenolics content of some Nepalese medicinal plants. Am J Plant Sci, 2013;4:1660-1667.
34. Liu H, Qiu N, Ding H, Yao R. polyphenol content and antioxidant capacity of 68 Chinese herbals suitable for medical or food uses. Food Res Int, 2008;41:363-370.
35. Amensour A, Sendra E, Abrini J, Perez-Alvarez JA, Fernandez-Lopez J. Antioxidant activity and total phenolic compounds of myrtle extracts. CyTA-J food, 2010;8:95-101.
36. McCord JM, Fridovich I. Superoxide dismutase. An enzymic function for erythrocyte (hemocuprein). J BiolChem, 1969;244:6049-6055.
37. Navabi SM, Navabi SF, Setzer WN, Alinezhad H, Zare M, Naqinezhad A. Interaction of different extracts of *Primula heterochromastaph.* With Red Blood Cell membrane lipids and proteins: antioxidant and antihaemolytic effects. J Diet Suppl, 2012;9:285-292
38. Dai F, Miao Q, Zhou B, Yang L, and Liu ZL. Protective effects of flavanols and their glycosides against free radical- induced oxidative haemolysis of red blood cells. Life Sci, 2006;78:2488-2493.
39. Chaudhuri S, Banerjee A, Basu K, Sengupta B, Sengupta PK. Interaction of flavonoid with red blood membrane lipids and proteins: antioxidant and antihemolytic activity. IntJ bio Macromol, 2007;41:42-48.
40. Romani A, Vignolini P, Isolani L, Ieri F, Heimler D. 2006. HPLC-DAD/MS characterization of flavonoids and hydroxycinnamic derivatives in turnip tops (*Brassica rapa* L. Subsp. *sylvestris* L.). J Agric Food Chem, 2006;54:1342-1346.
41. Tenore GC, Troisi J, Di Fiore R, Basile A, Novellino E. Chemical composition, antioxidant and antimicrobial properties of Rapa CatozzaNapoletana (*Brassica rapa* L. var. *rapaDC.*) seed meal, a promising protein source of Campania region (southern Italy) horticultural germplasm. J Sci Food Agric, 2012;92:1716-1724.
42. Jean-Gilles D, Li L, Ma H, Yuan T, Chichester CO, Seeram NP. 2012. Anti-inflammatory effects of polyphenolic-enriched red raspberry extract in an antigen-induced arthritis rat model. J Agric Food Chem, 2012;6:5755-5762.
43. Jin, J.H., Kim, J.S., Kang, S.S., Son, K.H., Chang, H.W. and Kim, H.P. 2010. Anti-inflammatory and anti-arthritic activity of total flavonoids of the roots of *Sophora flavescens*. J Ethnopharmacol, 2010;127:589-595.
44. Pan MH, Lai CS, Ho CT. Anti-inflammatory activity of natural dietary flavonoids. Food Funct, 2010;1:15-31.

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